

Fisher versus Neyman-Pearson Paradigm in Hypothesis Testing

Adel Mohammadpour*

Hossein Kazemzadeh G.*

Abstract

The Neyman-Pearson (NP) paradigm proposes the best test function that maximizes the power when the null hypothesis is true at a fixed size. On the other hand, Fisher linear discriminant analysis proposes an optimal test that minimizes the total hypothesis testing errors known as Bayes risk. Suppose the null and alternative hypotheses have no priority over each other. In that case the Fisher testing method, known as an optimal test, has none of the serious limitations of NP testing. However, it is not universal due to the computational complexity of the Bayes risk. Recently, we calculated Bayes risk analytically or numerically on the bayeserror.com. Now, we can find a critical region of optimal test and consider it as an alternative paradigm. We recall the mentioned paradigms, and prove that most of the hypothesis testing paradigms can be classify as one of these two paradigms.

Key Words: Neyman-Pearson lemma, Bayes risk, Optimal test, Bayes test, p -value.

1. Introduction

Financial maximization in economics is like risk minimization in statistics. This economic idea causes many human life problems. Many statisticians abandon risk minimization in hypothesis testing for replication and more broadly, in the biomedical and social sciences, McShane et al. (2019). Recall the problem of two prisoners in game theory. The prosecutor lacked hard evidence to convict both of them. Each prisoner has a choice between only two options: to stay silent or to betray the other. If both stay silent they have a lesser charge. Regardless of the other prisoner's chooses, each prisoner gets a higher reward for betraying the other. If any prisoner chose to betray or maximize their profits rather than remain silent, the consequences would be severe for them. Therefore, instead of maximizing profit, we can maximize the profit of both parties at the same time. These two approaches are similar to Neyman- Pearson and Fisher discriminant analysis paradigms, respectively.

Neyman-Pearson (NP) paradigm is the foundation of classical hypothesis testing. Fisher (1932) proposes minimizing the total of errors as a criterion in discriminant analysis. DeGroot (1975) introduces optimal hypothesis testing in his introductory textbook based on this idea. DeGroot's seminal idea is to establish a testing statistical hypothesis on minimizing the weighted sum of type I and II errors extended by Luis and Carlos (2013). He shows that NP lemma is a special case of the optimal test.

Classical hypothesis testing aims to strike a balance between minimizing Type I error, which involves incorrectly rejecting a true null hypothesis (H_0), and minimizing Type II errors, which involves incorrectly accepting a false alternative hypothesis (H_1). Typically, the default rate for Type I error is set, e.g., at five percent. However, in many scenarios, it is challenging to assigning significance to the hypotheses without prior beliefs regarding the truth of H_0 . This framework can be misguided as it assumes equal importance between hypotheses and might not reflect the real-world context.

An optimal test is a more general and natural idea to minimize the total errors rather than focusing solely on minimizing Type II error. This alternative approach offers a different paradigm for hypothesis testing, allowing for a more comprehensive evaluation of the hypotheses.

*Department of Statistics, Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, Amirkabir University of Technology (Tehran Polytechnic) and bayeserror.com

The following section introduce the best and optimal tests. In Section 2 we introduce the best and optimal tests procedures and paradigms. Section 3 presents two examples. Section 4 classifies and comparing different paradigms.

2. Hypothesis Testing

Let's focus on the problem of testing a simple null hypothesis H_0 against a simple alternative hypothesis H_1 . We denote by

$$\alpha = P_{H_0}(\text{reject } H_0) \text{ and } \beta = P_{H_1}(\text{reject } H_1)$$

the probability of type I and II errors, respectively. They are the probability of rejecting and accepting the null H_0 when true and false, respectively. (Here, $P_{H_0}(E)$ denotes the probability of an event E if H_0 is true.) Equivalently,

$$1 - \beta = P_{H_1}(\text{reject } H_0)$$

is the probability of correctly rejecting H_0 when H_1 is true, which is called the power of the test against H_1 . When designing a hypothesis test for testing H_0 versus H_1 , we have the following goal: maximize the power of the test against H_1 subject to the significance level of the test under H_0 is at most α . This is a constrained optimization problem, which we can reason about in the following way: Suppose we observe data which are realizations of continuous random variables X_1, \dots, X_n . For notational convenience, let us denote by $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, \dots, X_n)$ the entire data vector and by $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ a vector of possible values for \mathbf{X} . The hypotheses are

$$\begin{cases} H_0 : f(\mathbf{x}) = f_0(\mathbf{x}), \\ H_1 : f(\mathbf{x}) = f_1(\mathbf{x}). \end{cases}$$

Let \mathcal{X} denote the set of all possible values of \mathbf{X} under f_0 and f_1 . A rejection region $\mathcal{R} \subset \mathcal{X}$ such that we reject H_0 if the observed data belongs to \mathcal{R} . Then the probability of rejecting H_0 if H_0 were true would be $\int_{\mathcal{R}} f_0(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}$, the probability of rejecting H_0 if H_1 were true would be $\int_{\mathcal{R}} f_1(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}$. The above optimization problem is to choose $\mathcal{R} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ with the goal

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize } \int_{\mathcal{R}} f_1(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (\text{maximum power}) \\ & \text{subject to } \int_{\mathcal{R}} f_0(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \leq \alpha \quad (\text{significance level } \alpha). \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1 Neyman-Pearson. Let H_0 and H_1 be simple hypotheses. For a constant $k > 0$, suppose that the likelihood ratio test which rejects H_0 when $\phi(\mathbf{x}) = 1$, where

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } L(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{f_1(\mathbf{x})}{f_0(\mathbf{x})} > k \\ 0 & \text{if } L(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{f_1(\mathbf{x})}{f_0(\mathbf{x})} < k \end{cases}$$

$L(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{f_1(\mathbf{x})}{f_0(\mathbf{x})} > k$ has significance level α . Then for any other test of H_0 with a significance level at most α , its power against H_1 is at most the power of this likelihood ratio test.

Optimal Test. Suppose that a and b are specified positive constants. It is desired to find a test function ϕ for which $a\alpha_\phi + b\beta_\phi$ will be a minimum. The following result shows that a procedure that is optimal in this sense has a very simple form.

Theorem 1. Let ϕ^* denote a test procedure such that the hypothesis H_0 is accepted if

$a f_0(\mathbf{x}) > b f_1(\mathbf{x})$ and the hypothesis H_1 is accepted if $a f_0(\mathbf{x}) < b f_1(\mathbf{x})$. Either H_0 or H_1 may be accepted if $a f_0(\mathbf{x}) = b f_1(\mathbf{x})$. Then for any other test ϕ ,

$$a\alpha_{\phi^*} + b\beta_{\phi^*} \leq a\alpha_{\phi} + b\beta_{\phi}. \quad (1)$$

Definition 1 (Bayes test). Let H_0 and H_1 be simple hypotheses as above. A Bayesian rejection region $\mathcal{R}_B \subset \mathcal{X}$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{R}_B = \{\mathbf{x} : f_0(\mathbf{x}) < f_1(\mathbf{x})\}.$$

Bayes risk, James et al. (2021), is equal to

$$1 - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \max\{f_0(\mathbf{x}), f_1(\mathbf{x})\} d\mathbf{x} = \frac{\alpha_B + \beta_B}{2}.$$

Bayes test minimizes average error probabilities. A test with critical region \mathcal{R}_B has size α_B and minimizes total errors.

Corollary 1. Bayes test is optimal.

Proof. Set $a = b = \frac{1}{2}$ in Theorem 1. Then ϕ^* is a Bayes test.

Corollary 2. NP lemma is a special case of optimal test.

Proof. DeGroot (1975). Take $a = 1$ and $b = k$ in (1). From Theorem 1, it follows that for any other test procedure ϕ ,

$$\alpha_{\phi^*} + k\beta_{\phi^*} \leq \alpha_{\phi} + k\beta_{\phi}$$

If $\alpha_{\phi} \leq \alpha_{\phi^*}$, then it follows from the relation (1) that $\beta_{\phi} \geq \beta_{\phi^*}$. Also, if $\alpha_{\phi} < \alpha_{\phi^*}$, then it follows from the relation (1) that $\beta_{\phi} > \beta_{\phi^*}$. Therefore, ϕ^* is the best test.

Definition 2 (Test based on Null-Alternative p -Value, NAp -value). Let H_0 and H_1 be simple hypotheses as above. We reject H_0 if

$$P_{H_0}(L(\mathbf{X}) > L(\mathbf{x})) < P_{H_1}(L(\mathbf{X}) > L(\mathbf{x})).$$

Theorem 2. Take $k = 1$ in NP-Lemma. Then critical region, size and power of the tests based on NP, NAp -value, and Bayes test with a uniform prior are the same.

Note. A few authors assume that the hypotheses may be fuzzy or random. Mohammadpour and Mohammad-Djafari (2006) show that the best test for fuzzy or random hypotheses is equivalent to Neyman-Pearson lemma in classical statistics. Therefore, these paradigms are redundant.

3. Examples

Example 1. Let $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\theta, 1)$ and x be an observation from X . Assume $f_0(x)$ and $f_1(x)$ follow $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and $\mathcal{N}(1, 1)$, respectively. How do we choose between f_0 and f_1 on the basis of a single observation? The most powerful test has a critical region of the form

$$\frac{f_1(x)}{f_0(x)} \geq k.$$

Let

$$L(x) = \frac{f_1(x)}{f_0(x)} = \exp\left(\frac{-((x-1)^2 - x^2)}{2}\right),$$

which is an increasing function of x . Hence $L(x) \geq k$ and it follows that $\mathcal{R} = \{x : x \geq k'\}$. Thus a very large value of X is observed, we suspect that H_1 is true rather than H_0 . This is consistent with the fact that f_1 is shifted to the right version of f_0 . The size is given by

$$\alpha = P_{f_0}(\mathcal{R}) = \int_{x \geq k'} (1/\sqrt{2\pi}) e^{-x^2/2} dx = P(Z \geq k') = 1 - \Phi(k'),$$

Table 1: Percentage of chosen between $H_0 : X \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ versus $H_1 : X \sim \mathcal{N}(1, 1)$ correctly. The best values for each column are bolded.

Generated data under	H_0	H_1	H_0 or H_1 (randomly)
NP $\alpha = 0.05$	95	26	61
NP $\alpha = 0.5$	50	84	67
NP $k = 1$	69	69	69
Bayes $\alpha_B = 0.31$	69	69	69
NAp-value	69	69	69

where Z is a standard normal random variable with distribution function Φ , $\Phi(z_\alpha) = \alpha$, and $k' = z_{1-\alpha}$. The power is given by

$$P_{f_1}(\mathcal{R}) = \int_{x \geq z_{1-\alpha}} (1/\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-(x-1)^2/2} dx = 1 - \Phi(z_{1-\alpha} - 1).$$

To calculate Bayes risk, we should determine the cross point of two densities f_0 and f_1 which can be find using the following equation:

$$(1/\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-x^2/2} = (1/\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-(x-1)^2/2}.$$

Therefore, $x = 0.5$ and $\mathcal{R}_B = (0.5, \infty)$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Bayes risk} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{0.5} (1/\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-x^2/2} dx + 1 - \int_{0.5}^{\infty} (1/\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-(x-1)^2/2} dx \right) \\ &= \frac{1 - \Phi(0.5) + \Phi(-0.5)}{2} = \frac{0.3085375 + 0.3085375}{2} = 0.3085375. \end{aligned}$$

Table 1 presents the acceptance percentage of a hypothesis correctly, H_0 or H_1 . When two hypotheses have no priority, NP with $k = 1$, NAp-value, or Bayes test has the same result, and all of them minimize total errors.

Example 2. Testing Normal Against Double Exponential. Suppose X has density function

$$f_0(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left\{-\frac{x^2}{2}\right\}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}$$

under H_0 and

$$f_1(x) = \frac{1}{2} \exp\{-|x|\}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}$$

under H_1 . Let

$$L(x) = \frac{f_1(x)}{f_0(x)} = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{2} \exp\left\{-|x| + \frac{x^2}{2}\right\}.$$

We note that

$$\frac{x^2}{2} - |x| = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) (x^2 - 2|x| + 1 - 1) = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) [(|x| - 1)^2 - 1]$$

so that

$$L(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{-1/2} e^{(|x|-1)^2/2},$$

which is an increasing function of $||x| - 1|$. Hence

$$L(x) \geq k \quad \text{if and only if } ||x| - 1| \geq k'$$

and it follows that \mathcal{R} is of the form $\mathcal{R} = \{x : |x| \geq k_1 \text{ or } |x| \leq k_2\}$. Thus if either a very large or a very small value of X is observed, we suspect that H_1 is true rather than H_0 . This is consistent with the fact that f_1 has more probability in its tails and near zero than f_0 has. The size is given by

$$\begin{aligned} P_{f_0}(\mathcal{R}) &= \int_{|x| \geq k_1} (1/\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-x^2/2} dx + \int_{|x| \leq k_2} (1/\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-x^2/2} dx \\ &= 2(P(Z \geq k_1) + P(0 < Z \leq k_2)), \end{aligned}$$

where Z has a standard normal distribution. The power is given by

$$\begin{aligned} P_{f_1}(\mathcal{R}) &= \int_{|x| \geq k_1} \frac{e^{-|x|}}{2} dx + \int_{|x| \leq k_2} \frac{e^{-|x|}}{2} dx \\ &= e^{-k_1} + 1 - e^{-k_2}. \end{aligned}$$

4. Classify Hypothesis Testing Paradigm

Table 2 presents nine elements of three hypothesis testing paradigm procedures. We consider three main classical, Bayesian, and evidential paradigms.

Table 2: Hypothesis testing procedure elements for three paradigm

Elements	Paradigm		
	Classical	Bayesian	Evidential
Criteria	Mostly 0-1 Loss	Loss	$-\log$ Likelihood
Optimization	Fixed α & Min β	Min $\alpha + \beta$	Min α & β
Solution	Theoretically	Theoretically	Open
Calculation	Calculated	Estimated	Approximated
Computation	Manually	Software	Experimentally
Tool	P -Value	Bayes Risk	Error Bound.
Prior on	Hypotheses	Parameters	N/A
Need Data	Yes	Yes/No	Yes
Real App.	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 3 classifies various paradigms based on the results of Section 2. This table helps us to simplify the procedure of hypothesis testing using the equivalence of these paradigms. Software for computing Bayes risk should be used to find an optimal test. However, NAp -value is a shortcut instead of Bayes risk computation. The proposed procedures can be extended to one side hypothesis. But the two sides hypotheses need more caution.

Table 3: Paradigm Clustering Frameworks

Classical	Bayesian	Evidential
Neyman–Pearson Neyman & Pearson (1933)	Discriminant Analysis Fisher (1936)	Evidential HT Royall (1997)
Permutation test Fisher (1935)	Bayesian HT	Relative Belief (Evans (1997))
Fuzzy HT	Bayesian Fuzzy HT	Fiducial HT
Fisher Paradigm	Optimal Data Analysis Yarnold et al. (2010)	

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